

USN UNIVERSAL BARCODE-READY PCR2 SYSTEM FOR ION TORRENT

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1. ABSTRACT

This protocol describes a two-step PCR barcoding workflow developed at the University of South-Eastern Norway. PCR1 uses locus-specific primers with universal overhangs, and PCR2 introduces custom USN-designed barcodes and full Ion Torrent adapters. The method provides a flexible, modular, and contamination-aware approach for preparing sequencing-ready amplicon libraries.

2. KEYWORDS

metabarcoding; barcoding; Ion Torrent; PCR2; adapters; USN barcodes; sequencing workflow

3. SUMMARY

This protocol outlines a modular two-step metabarcoding workflow. PCR1 amplifies the target locus using primers with universal overhangs, and PCR2 adds full sequencing adapters and sample-specific barcodes through custom USN-designed forward and reverse primers, producing Ion Torrent-ready amplicon libraries without ligation.

4. PCR1 (GENERAL)

PCR1 depends on the chosen primer pair for the target locus (e.g., COImini, 18S, MiFish). All PCR1 primers must include the following universal overhangs:

Forward overhang: 5'-TCGTCGGCAG-3'

Reverse overhang: 5'-GTCTCGTGGG-3'

PCR conditions should follow the established specifications for the selected locus.

5. PCR2 (BARCODING)

Custom USN-designed barcoded primers (forward & reverse) are used in PCR2.

PCR2 reaction mix (25 µL)

- 12.5 µL 2× KAPA Taq HotStart ReadyMix
- 0.5 µL Forward primer (10 µM)

- 0.5 μ L Reverse primer (10 μ M)
- 1 μ L PCR1 template
- Nuclease-free water to 25 μ L

PCR2 reaction mix (12.5 μ L)

- 6.3 μ L 2 \times KAPA Taq HotStart ReadyMix
- 0.3 μ L Forward primer (10 μ M)
- 0.3 μ L Reverse primer (10 μ M)
- 0.5 μ L PCR1 template
- 3.1 μ L water (total = 12.5 μ L)

PCR2 barcoding program (English)

1) Initial denaturation: 95°C for 3:00

2) 5 cycles:

- 95°C for 0:20
- 50°C for 0:30
- 72°C for 0:45

3) 12 cycles:

- 95°C for 0:20
- 55°C for 0:30
- 72°C for 0:45

4) Final extension: 72°C for 2:00, then hold at 4°C

PCR2 products are verified on gel prior to pooling and sequencing.

6. HOW TO CITE THIS PROTOCOL

Sevatdal, S.G. & Sønstebø, J.H. (2026). USN Universal Barcode-Ready PCR2 System for Ion Torrent. Zenodo. Version 1.0.

7. APPENDIX: PRIMER TABLES

PCR1_F primers

Name	Sequence (5'->3')	Comment
F_PCR1_U	TCGTCGGCAG	Forward universal overhang
R_PCR1_U	GTCTCGTGGG	Reverse universal overhang

PCR2_F primers

Name	Sequence (5'->3')	Comment
F_PCR2_BC01	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGACGAGTGCCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC01 barcode
F_PCR2_BC02	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGACGCTCGACATCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC02 barcode
F_PCR2_BC03	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGAGACGCACTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC03 barcode
F_PCR2_BC04	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGAGCACTGTAGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC04 barcode
F_PCR2_BC05	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGATCAGACACGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC05 barcode
F_PCR2_BC06	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGATATCGCGAGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC06 barcode
F_PCR2_BC07	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGCGTGTCTCTATCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC07 barcode
F_PCR2_BC08	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGCTCGCGTGTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC08 barcode
F_PCR2_BC09	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGGTCACGTACTTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC09 barcode
F_PCR2_BC10	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGGTCTCTGATGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC10 barcode
F_PCR2_BC11	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTCTACGTAGCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC11 barcode
F_PCR2_BC12	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTGATACGTCTTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC12 barcode
F_PCR2_BC13	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTGGAGGACACTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC13 barcode
F_PCR2_BC14	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTTCACACCTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC14 barcode
F_PCR2_BC15	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTTCTCGTGGTTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC15 barcode
F_PCR2_BC16	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTTCGCGCAGTTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC16 barcode
F_PCR2_BC17	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGAACGCGTGATTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC17 barcode
F_PCR2_BC18	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGAACTCGTCACTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A-adapter + BC18 barcode

F_PCR2_BC19	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGAGACGTCCACTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC19 barcode
F_PCR2_BC20	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGAGCACTGAGCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC20 barcode
F_PCR2_BC21	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGATCAGCGAGTTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC21 barcode
F_PCR2_BC22	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGATATCGCGCATCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC22 barcode
F_PCR2_BC23	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGCGTGTCTGTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC23 barcode
F_PCR2_BC24	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGCTCGTCCGTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC24 barcode
F_PCR2_BC25	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGGTCACGTCACTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC25 barcode
F_PCR2_BC26	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGGTCTCGTAGTTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC26 barcode
F_PCR2_BC27	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTCTACGTCACTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC27 barcode
F_PCR2_BC28	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTGATCGAGTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC28 barcode
F_PCR2_BC29	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTGGAGTCGTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC29 barcode
F_PCR2_BC30	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTTCACGTCACTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC30 barcode
F_PCR2_BC31	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTTCTCGTCAGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC31 barcode
F_PCR2_BC32	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTTCGCGTGTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC32 barcode
F_PCR2_BC33	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGAACGCGTCAGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC33 barcode
F_PCR2_BC34	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGAACTCGTCTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC34 barcode
F_PCR2_BC35	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGAGACGTGCTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC35 barcode
F_PCR2_BC36	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGAGCACTGTGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC36 barcode
F_PCR2_BC37	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGATCAGCGTCTTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC37 barcode
F_PCR2_BC38	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGATATCGTCTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC38 barcode
F_PCR2_BC39	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGCGTGTCTGAGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC39 barcode
F_PCR2_BC40	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGCTCGTCGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC40 barcode
F_PCR2_BC41	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGGTCACGTCACTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC41 barcode
F_PCR2_BC42	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGGTCTCGTCTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC42 barcode

F_PCR2_BC43	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTCTACGTCAGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC43 barcode
F_PCR2_BC44	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTGATCGTCTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC44 barcode
F_PCR2_BC45	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTGGAGTCGAGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC45 barcode
F_PCR2_BC46	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTTCACGTCAGTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC46 barcode
F_PCR2_BC47	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTTCTCGTCTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC47 barcode
F_PCR2_BC48	CCATCTCATCCCTGCGTGTCTCCGACTC AGTTCGCGTCTCTCGTCGGCAG	Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter + BC48 barcode
		Forward PCR2 primer with A- adapter without barcode

PCR2_R primers

Name	Sequence (5'->3')	Comments
R_PCR2_RB01	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATTCGATACGTAGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB01 barcode
R_PCR2_RB02	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATGACTTGCATAGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB02 barcode
R_PCR2_RB03	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATATGCCAGTTCGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB03 barcode
R_PCR2_RB04	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATCAGTATGCTGGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB04 barcode
R_PCR2_RB05	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATGTACGATCTTGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB05 barcode
R_PCR2_RB06	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATTACGCTAGACGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB06 barcode
R_PCR2_RB07	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATCGTATCAGTTGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB07 barcode
R_PCR2_RB08	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATAGTCTGACGTGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB08 barcode
R_PCR2_RB09	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATTGCATGACTAGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB09 barcode
R_PCR2_RB10	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATGATCTACGTCGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB10 barcode

R_PCR2_RB11	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATCTAGTCGATAGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB11 barcode
R_PCR2_RB12	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATACAGTCTGTAGTCT CGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter + RB12 barcode
R_PCR2_fullP1_u niv	CCACTACGCCTCCGCTTTCCTCTCTATG GGCAGTCGGTGATGTCTCGTGGG	Reverse PCR2 primer with trP1 adapter without barcode